

An Overview of Border-Related Policies Introduced by the Russian Federation in response to the COVID-19 Pandemic during 2020

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Background

Immigration to the Russian Federation is controlled by the Main Directorate for Migration Affairs, which replaced the Federal Migration Service in 2016. Travel policy in Russia is controlled by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

This report provides an overview of the immigration-related policies implemented by the Russian Federation to combat COVID-19 in 2020. The country responded early to the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic with travel restrictions, beginning with a partial border closure and followed by a series of visa bans, international flight suspensions, and additional border closures. Many of these restrictions were lifted beginning in July 2020.

Travel and Migration Policies

As early as January 2020, during the earliest stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Russian federation began restricting travel to slow the spread of the virus.

On 28-Jan, Prime Minister Mikhail Mishustin announced that Russia's land border with China was to be closed from 31-Jan until at least 1-Mar.

In the following months, the Russian Federation issued a series of travel, border, and visa restrictions as the pandemic worsened worldwide. Starting 19-Feb, the Russian government restricted entry access and suspended visa applications for Chinese Nationals. On 28-Feb, the country announced a ban on entry for Iranian citizens regardless of visa status.

On 4-Mar, the Russian government suspended its train service to Nice, France and on 9-Mar, air service to and from Hong Kong. And on 15-Mar, the Russian Railways halted service from Moscow to Berlin, Germany and Paris, France and closed land borders with Norway and Poland.

On 13-Mar, the government issued a visa suspension for Italian nationals. On 16-Mar, the government introduced a series of travel restrictions including a complete border closure to foreign nationals and a suspension of most commercial flights to and from European Union member states. On 18-Mar, Russia announced a temporary ban on entry for all foreign travelers with exceptions

made for Russian citizens, diplomatic staff, international truck drivers, airline crews, and visa holders entering the country on account of a relative's death. This restriction was set to expire on 1-May, but was extended indefinitely effective 2-May. The policy ultimately ended on 1-Oct, 2020.

The following weeks featured the implementation of increasingly restrictive policies. On 20-Mar, Russia suspended all flights to the United States, United Kingdom, and United Arab Emirates. On 25-Mar, several international flights were suspended, and those that were still operational were suspended on 31-Mar when Russia temporarily ended all commercial airline flights, allowing only limited charter flights to continue for repatriation purposes. On 30-Mar, Russia implemented an indefinite, complete ban on passenger travel via its land borders.

Starting in June, the Russian Federation began to ease the restrictions put in place to combat COVID-19. Foreigners requiring medical treatment in Russia and those seeking entry to take care of sick relatives were granted permission to enter from 13-June onward. Then, on 1-Aug, Russia resumed flights to Britain, Turkey, and Tanzania. And on 5-Aug, diplomatic visa holders were allowed to enter the country.

Russia began gradually resuming more flights toward the end of August, beginning with specific exceptions for foreign participants in the Russian Grand Prix (21-Aug) and other foreign athletes, coaches, and fitness specialists (26-Aug).

On 2-Sept, Prime Minister Mishustin implemented a directive with the governments of Egypt, United Arab Emirates, and the Maldives to steadily increase flight service. On 9-Sept, he further allowed Russian nationals to leave the country for medical purposes, like the earlier 13-June directive. On 1-Aug, flights to and from Britain, Turkey, and Tanzania resumed and flights to and from Britain, Egypt, and the United Arab Emirates resumed on 3-Sept.

Seaports reopened on 15-Sept, and several days later, on 21-Sept, Russia resumed flights with service to and from Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Belarus. Service to and from South Korea resumed on 27-Sept.

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